

Conference Abstract

Limnophilic Fish Species in Slovakia: the Red List Status and Threats

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Abstract

Between 2021 and 2023, the conservation status of all native fish and lamprey species in Slovakia was revised for the forthcoming edition of the National Red List (currently in press). In this paper, we focus on the status of limnophilic fish species, including *Carassius carassius*, *Leucaspis delineatus*, *Misgurnus fossilis*, *Umbra krameri* and *Tinca tinca*. The aforementioned species, were once widespread but has experienced significant decrease. The assessment is primarily based on data from permanently monitored sites maintained by the State Nature Conservancy of the Slovak Republic, as well as additional data provided by the Slovak Water Research Institute (WRI). Based on data and the documented alterations that have transpired over the past two decades, *C. carassius* (criteria A2-a,b,c,e; B1-a,b(iv)) and *U. krameri* (A4-a,c,e; B1-b(ii,iv)) have been designated as Critically Endangered. The following species - *L. delineatus* (A2-a,b,c,e; B1-b(iii,iv)); *M. fossilis* (A2-a,b,c; B1-a,b(iii,iv)) were assessed as Endangered. The species *M. fossilis* and *C. carassius* have moved up two threat categories compared to the previous Red List status (Koščo and Holčík 2008). Species *U. krameri* has moved up one category, from Endangered (EN) to Critically Endangered (CR). The threat categories of *L. delineatus* and *T. tinca* have remained unchanged. The species *T. tinca* was categorized as Near Threatened, primarily due to its restricted current distribution in areas surrounding water reservoirs and ponds (breeding and stocking impact). The status of natural populations of *T. tinca* is not actively monitored in Slovakia. Habitat loss, reduced flooding, and the intensive breeding and stocking of commercial fish species

remain common threats to all studied species. These pressures are currently being intensified by climate change and increasing demands on water resources. Specific and localized threats to limnophilic fish species include hybridization and backcrossing, the impact of invasive alien fish species, transfer of bait fish, removal of aquatic vegetation and sediments, the release of exotic aquarium species, or/and insufficient monitoring (Suppl. material 1).

Presenting author

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Poster [doi](#)

Authors: Jakub Fedorčák, Peter Križek, Ján Koščo

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